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ABSTRACT

The capacity of the agricultural landscape to provide soil-based ecosystem services (SESs) is directly related to the condition of soils and their properties and functions. Soil and SESs are threatened by rapid environmental changes and anthropic activities identified as the so-called soil threats (STs). The STs are processes that could degrade the soil functions and services. Moreover, SESs and STs do not vary independently; they co-occur as bundles in a given spatial-temporal scale. At the European Union (EU) level, there is a growing recognition of the importance of the spatial quantification and mapping of SESs and STs bundles and their evolution under climate and land use change scenarios. This report analyses the existing attempts for mapping SES, STs and bundles in arable land at European scale and mapping their evolution under different scenarios (SERENA Tasks 5.1 and 5.2), based on a systematic review of the scientific literature. The literature review was carried out on Scopus and Web of Science databases with a list of keywords that yielded respectively 224 references for SESs and 1217 for STs. After the elimination of redundant references and the screening of the titles, abstracts and full texts, only 11 SES articles and 26 ST articles were considered appropriate. In addition, five technical reports were added to the results; in total 13 SES and 29 ST documents were analyzed following different axes: ES and SES classification produced by Serena, assessment and mapping approaches. The most commonly mapped SESs and STs were: erosion control (31%), green greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration (26%), soil erosion (51%) and soil contamination (10%). Only four articles regarding the evolution of SESs and STs under different scenarios of climate and/or land use change were encountered. They consider soil loss by water erosion and loss of SOC as STs, and SOC stock and SOC uptake as SESs. Two articles focusing on synergies and trade-offs and one on bundles were encountered. Ten SES and 19 ST potential indicators were identified. Overall, conceptual, deterministic and statistical models were the most frequently used for SES assessment. In addition, spatially explicit indicators mapped from literature and statistics were the most frequently used to map SESs. For STs, deterministic models, statistical models and expert knowledge were the most frequently used. The most reliable approaches for assessment and mapping SES and ST based their validations in data splitting and cross-validation.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

EEA: European Environmental Agency
EU: European Union
ES: Ecosystem Service
ESDB: European Soil Database
ESF: Ecosystem Service Function
JRC: Joint Research Centre
MLRM: Multinomial Logistic Regression Model
NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OC: Organic Carbon
PCA: Principal Component Analysis
PESERA: Pan European Soil Erosion Risk Assessment
PESS: Primary and secondary biomass, as provisioning ecosystem services
PTRDB: Pedo-Transfer Rules Database
RUSLE: Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
RWEQ: Revised Wind Erosion Equation Model
SES: Soil Ecosystem Service
SOC: Soil Organic Carbon
SOM: Soil Organic Matter
ST: Soil threat

1 Introduction

Ecosystem services are the direct and indirect contributions of an ecosystem to human well-being (TEEB, 2010). Soil is the basis of terrestrial ecosystems. In this sense, most ecosystem services necessary for the maintenance of terrestrial environmental and ecological systems, including human life, arise from the soil (Kibblewhite et al., 2008). The soil ecosystem services (SESs) are the subset of ecosystem services directly and quantifiably controlled or provided by soils and their chemical, physical and biological properties, processes and functions (Paul et al., 2021). However, soil and SESs are threatened by rapid environmental changes and anthropic activities identified as the so-called soil threats (STs). The STs are processes that could degrade the soil functions and services (SERENA definition, Annex II). Soil erosion, soil organic carbon loss, nutrient imbalance, soil acidification, soil contamination, compaction, soil sealing, soil salinization, loss of diversity are among the most important soil threats in agricultural landscapes (SERENA project; Annex I). Furthermore, SESs and STs interact and co-occur, as a consequence bundles of SESs or STs were defined as the set of ecosystem services and threats, or the combination of the two, that appear together repeatedly in space and time, related to a specific context (Potschin-Young et al., 2018).

In the European Union, agricultural land plays an important role in land use patterns across the continent. Cropland and Grassland account for 39% of the land cover (European Environment Agency., 2017). However, the degradation of agroecosystems caused by long term agronomic management practices, land take (i.e., conversion of the land to settlements and infrastructure) and climate change has economic consequences and considerable negative environmental impacts (Rendon et al., 2022). Consequently, there is the growing need of information about SESs and STs, as shown by the European policies in climate change mitigation and adaptation and the European Green Deal strategy (Fleming & Mauger, 2021). Thus, identifying indicators, mapping SESs, STs, bundles, and forecasting their evolution under different scenarios (climate and land cover changes) at European scale, is of great importance, especially, to determine soil long-term resilience and ability to sustain our well-being (Rendon et al., 2022). In this regard, the comprehension of SES and ST assessment and modelling methods at the European scale is essential for understanding the SES and ST interactions and allow the possibility to make spatial representation of such interactions through maps which are essential for decision making (Burkhard & Maes, 2017).

In Europe, the tentative of mapping bundles of SESs and STs is rare and incomplete (Jopke et al., 2015; Maes et al., 2012a; Mouchet et al., 2017; Orsi et al., 2020; Plieninger et al., 2019; Ungaro et al., 2022). Although there is a growing body of knowledge available on SES and ST interactions (i.e., at country and regional scale), the complexity and interaction of multiple SESs and STs and the forecasting under land use and climate change scenarios in agricultural landscape at continent scale, still need to be explored. To address this issue, the SERENA project (Soil ecosystem services and soil threats modelling and mapping) was launched in November 2021. The SERENA project attempts to strengthen the soil policy effectiveness by *“assess(ing), analyz(ing) and map(ping) SESs bundles across European agricultural landscapes, highlighting how soil threats affects the supply of services bundles through adoption of a set of site-specific reference thresholds”*.

This report presents the state of the art of existing studies for agricultural soils on (i) the mapping attempts of SESs and STs at the European scale, individually or in interactions, and (ii) the mapping attempts of the evolution of bundles of SESs and STs under different scenarios, i.e., climate, land use, and management change. The list of seven SESs and the eleven STs of interest for the SERENA project (Annex I) was used as a reference to select and classify the SESs and STs found in the articles. The following SESs were identified by this report: erosion control, greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration, primary/biomass production, hydrological control and habitat for

biodiversity. In addition, STs were identified as follows: soil erosion, soil contamination, soil organic carbon loss, soil compaction, salinization, soil sealing, soil drought, nutrient imbalance, soil acidification, waterlogging and loss of diversity. The report is organized into nine sections and extended annexes. The methods section details the literature search, screening, information extraction, database building, and data treatment. The database content section describes the bibliographic information (i.e., publication year and journal disciplines) and land uses in the mapping attempts. The “SESs and STs” section provide the soil ecosystem services and threats gathered. The section on indicators and methods used to map SESs and STs and soil threats provides and analyses the indicators used for the mapping attempts, followed by the methods used to assess and map SESs and STs. The section SES and ST interaction describe the information regarding SES and ST bundles, synergies, and tradeoff. The section mapping soil ecosystem services and threats under different scenarios gives an overview of the evolution and forecasting of SESs and STs under land management and climate change. Finally, final considerations, references, and appendices are provided.

2 Methods

2.1 Literature search

We conducted a systematic literature search following the ROSES framework (Haddaway et al., 2018). The literature search was carried out on Scopus and Web of Science citation databases, the 25th of April 2022. The queries used are reported in Table 1. Essentially, the terms related to SESs, STs, bundles, scenarios, mapping or modeling in arable land, pasture and grassland at a European scale were used in these queries. The publication list resulting from these queries was stored in the open reference management software Zotero (version 6.0.8). These queries harvested respectively 224 references for SESs and 1217 for STs.

Table 1. Queries used for the literature search on Scopus and Web of Science

Topic	Database	Keywords	Number of articles
SES	Scopus	Search: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("soil ecosystem service mapping*" OR "map*" OR "soil based ecosystem service*" OR "model*" OR "modeling*" OR "assessment*" OR "ecosystem condition*" OR "bundles*") AND ("pastures*" OR "grassland*" OR "arable land*" OR "agriculture*" OR "agroecosystem*") AND ("environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR "landscape service*" OR "ecosystem function*" OR "environmental function*") AND ("global chang*" OR "climate change*" OR "land use change*" OR "land us*" OR "land cover*" OR "land management?" OR "management?") AND ("Europe*" OR "European scale*") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE, "Agriculture Ecosystems and Environment") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Trade-off")	103
	Web of science	Search: TS=("soil ecosystem service mapping*" OR "map*" OR "soil based ecosystem service*" OR "model*" OR "modeling*" OR "assessment*" OR "ecosystem condition*" OR "bundles*") AND TS= ("pastures*" OR "grassland*" OR "arable land*" OR "agriculture*" OR "agroecosystem*") AND TS= ("environmental service*" OR "ecological service*" OR "landscape service*" OR "ecosystem function*" OR "environmental function*") AND TS= ("Europe*" OR "European scale*") AND TS= ("global chang*" OR "climate change*" OR "land use change*" OR "land use*" OR "land cover*" OR "land management?*" OR "management?*")	121
ST	Scopus	Search: TITLE-ABS-KEY("soil threat mapping*" OR "map soil threat*" OR "map*" OR "mapping*" OR "model*" OR "modeling*") AND ("bundles*" OR "assessment*" OR "quantifying*") AND ("soil toxic elements*" OR "soil organic carbon loss*" OR "soil erosion*" OR "soil sealing*" OR "nutrient imbalance*" OR "Soil acidification*" OR "soil contamination*" OR "soil compaction*" OR "salinization*" OR "loss of diversity*") AND ("pastures*" OR "grassland*" OR "arable land*" OR "agriculture*" OR "agroecosystem*") AND ("scenari*" OR "land use scenario*") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("global chang*" OR	976

		"climate change*" OR "land use change*" OR "land us*" OR "land cover*" OR "land management?" OR "management?") AND ("Europe*" OR "European scale*") AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Heavy Metals") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Agricultural Management") AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD, "Soil Pollution"))	
Web of science		Search: TS= ("soil threat mapping*" OR "map soil threat*" OR "map*" OR "mapping*" OR "model*" OR "modelling*") AND ("bundles*" OR "assessment*" OR "Quantifying*") AND TS= ("soil toxic elements*" OR "soil organic carbon loss*" OR "soil erosion*" OR "soil sealing*" OR "nutrient imbalance*" OR "Soil acidification*" OR "soil contamination*" OR "soil compaction*" OR "salinization*" OR "loss of diversity*") AND TS= ("pastures*" OR "grassland*" OR "arable land*" OR "agriculture*" OR "agroecosystem*") AND TS= ("scenari*" OR "land use scenario*") AND TS= ("global chang*" OR "climate change*" OR "land use change*" OR land use*" OR "land cover*" OR "land management?*" OR "management?*") AND TS= ("Europe*" OR "European scale*")	241

2.2 Literature screening

A total of 224 and 1217 references on SESs and STs, respectively, was obtained and screened in the following five steps:

- 1- A selection process to remove the duplicate results;
- 2- A title screening using the list of search terms as a reference. Articles were selected if they met at least one of the requested keywords.
- 3- An abstract screening. We selected the articles that included keywords related to mapping attempts of SESs, STs, bundles, or forecasting scenarios (climate and land cover changes) in agroecosystems at the European scale.
- 4- A first full-text screening to ensure that the collected articles included assessment, modeling, and spatial representation of SESs, STs, interactions, or forecasting.
- 5- A second full-text screening attempt. In the first full-text screening, the selected articles included mapping attempts of soil properties that were assessed and modelled instead of indicators of SESs and STs. We removed those papers (Figure 1).

After the screening steps, only 11 articles on SESs and 26 articles on STs remained. Finally, five technical reports, two on SESs and three on STs were added to the results. The technical reports on SESs were published by the joint research centre (JRC) and LANDMARK deliverable Task 4.2. The technical reports related to STs were published by JRC and the institute of geodesy, cartography, and remote sensing (FÖMI) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. In total, 13 SES and 29 ST documents were analyzed.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the document selection

2.3 Information extraction and database building

A summary excel file sheet was used to gather the information contained in the kept documents. For the selected literature items, we collected information on five levels (Figure 2):

- (1) Bibliographic information on each article or technical report.
- (2) Land use/cover addressed in the document. In this sense, we selected articles dealing with agricultural areas (arable land, permanent crops, pastures and heterogeneous agricultural areas), mixed agricultural-natural and mixed agricultural-natural-urban land uses (based on the CORINE land

cover classification). To cover all the available information on agricultural land at European scale, the “mixed” categories were included.

(3) Total number of SESs and STs considered, as well their interactions when provided.

(4) Indicators used to make the spatial representation of the selected SESs and STs.

(5) The methods level refers to all the information related to the method of assessment, modelling and mapping SESs, STs, interactions and scenarios.

1. Bibliographic

Publication year, document type.

2. The context of the study

Land use: arable land, permanent crops, pastures and heterogeneous agricultural areas, arable land and forest and arable land, forest and urban land uses.

3. SESs and STs considered

Number and type of SESs and STs, considered individually or in group.

4. SES/ST indicators

Key indicators used to model and mapping.

5. Methods of assessment and mapping

- SES and ST methods of assessment, considered individually or in group.
- Bundles type of analysis and assessment.
- Mapping methods.
- Methodological approach for SESs/STs evolution under different scenarios.
- Type of scenario (climate and land cover changes).
- Model validation

3 Database content

3.1 Bibliographic information

The SES publications are recent, whereas the ST publications have a relatively long history (Figure 3). The first attempt at mapping SESs at a continental scale was published in 2011. The maximum number of articles per year (two) was published in 2012, 2018 and 2019, while the remaining documents were published one per year since 2014 to 2022. On the other hand, the first attempt at mapping STs at a continental scale was published in 1999. In 2008, after nine years, the second document was published. The year 2014 had the maximum number of published documents (four), followed by 2016, 2018 and 2022 (three). The published documents are spread over a total of 26 academic journals and three repositories for technical reports (Annex III). This indicates that mapping efforts at the continental

scale have been focused on processes derived from STs while less importance has been given to the spatial SESs interactions and forecasting.

Figure 3. Publication year of journal articles and technical reports, reporting mapping attempts of SESs (n=13) and STs (n=29) at the European scale

3.2 Land uses

We adopted the classification of CORINE land cover to define the land use categories suitable to select the articles (Figure 4), since agricultural land use was often considered in association to other land uses. In the selection of SESs, four documents concerned arable land and permanent crops. Arable land and forest accounted for seven articles. In contrast, only two documents consider arable land, forest and urban land uses. The previous result indicates that in total eight articles accounted for ESs provided by agricultural, forest and urban land use. In general, those documents mapped SESs a long with non-soil-based ecosystem services (ESs). Thus, it was necessary to select articles considering SESs provided only in agricultural land use. In addition, the low number of documents evaluating SESs specifically in agriculture land use (four) indicates that more efforts should be focused on the assessment of ecosystem services provided explicitly by soil in agroecosystems at the EU scale.

In the selection of ST publications, 12 of them concerned arable land and permanent crops. The “arable land, forest and urban” categories accounted for 17 articles. STs are an essential research topic in the agricultural landscape, because the underlying agricultural systems provide significant drivers of soil and environmental degradation (Borrelli et al., 2020). For instance, plowing and unsustainable agricultural practices combined with overgrazing are the leading causes of human-induced soil erosion. Moreover, this triggers a series of cascade effects within the soil ecosystem, such as nutrient loss, soil organic carbon loss, declining biodiversity, and soil ecosystem stability (Robinson et al., 2017).

Figure 4. Land cover categories identified in the SESs (n=13) and STs (n=29) mapping attempts

4 Soil ecosystem services and soil threats considered in the gathered documents

The seven SESs and eleven STs of interest for the SERENA project (Annex I) were used as a reference to select and classify the SESs and STs encountered in the publications. We identified mapping attempts at the European scale for five and eleven of the SESs and STs respectively, listed by SERENA. The two most frequently mapped SESs are erosion control (seven articles) and greenhouse gas and climate regulation, including carbon sequestration (six articles). Primary/biomass production (three articles), hydrological control (one article and one report) and habitat for biodiversity (one article) were the least mapped SESs. The STs most frequently mapped are soil erosion (e.g., water, wind, tillage, sheet, rill, gully) (20 articles) followed by soil contamination (e.g., potentially toxic elements, organic pollutants, microplastics) (four articles), soil organic carbon loss (three articles), soil compaction (three articles) and salinization (three articles). In contrast, soil sealing (one report), soil drought (one report), nutrient imbalance (one article), soil acidification (one article), waterlogging (one article) and loss of diversity (one article) were the least frequently mapped (Figure 5), probably due to our criteria for the selection of land uses.

Mapping attempts at the continental scale for the following SESs were not encountered in the literature: environmental pollution control and pest and disease control. Mapping attempts of environmental pollution control at the continental scale in the agricultural landscape are missing. Whereas RECARE (preventing and remediating degradation of soils in Europe through land care) based JRC technical report "Soil threats in Europe status, methods, drivers and effects on ecosystem services" (Stolte et al., 2015), includes a chapter on soil pollution, but not a mapping attempt. Concerning pest and disease control, this SES has been incorporated as susceptibility to diseases in the MINOTAUR project (Modeling and mapping soil biodiversity patterns and functions across Europe) (MINOTAUR, 2021). However, pest and disease control were identified as the least essential or relevant for the SERENA project due to that just one country found it important (SERENA deliverable D2.2, 2022).

Figure 5. Proportion of mapping attempt for SES (n=13) and ST (n=29) at EU scale

5 Indicators and methods used to map the soil ecosystem services and soil threats at the European scale

5.1 Soil ecosystem service and soil threat indicators

In the selected documents we identified 10 SES and 19 ST indicators. Regarding SESs (Table 2), habitat for biodiversity (three), erosion control (two), hydrological control (two) and primary/biomass production (two) had the maximum number of indicators. Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration was mapped with one indicator. Regarding STs (Table 3), soil erosion (five), loss of diversity (three), soil contamination (three) had the maximum number of indicators. In contrast, soil organic carbon loss (one), soil compaction (one), salinization (one), soil sealing (one), soil drought (one), nutrient imbalance (one), soil acidification (one) and waterlogging (one) had the minimum number of indicators.

Habitat for biodiversity was mapped with composed indicators that represent soil biological and chemical attributes (Rutgers et al., 2019). Erosion control indicators provide information on the influence of vegetation in the decrease of erosion risk (Schulp et al., 2012) and soil retention based on RUSLE model (Maes et al., 2012; Rendon et al., 2022). Hydrological control indicators provide information of the potential of soil to retain and process pollutants and the water holding capacity. Primary/biomass production indicators were used to spatially represent the primary and secondary biomass production and the energy output from agricultural biomass. Finally, the greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration was mapped using the percentage of the annual total CO₂ emission that is captured by the ecosystem by Country.

Table 2. Indicators used to map SESs at EU scale

Soil ecosystem service	Indicator	Unit	Description	Reference
Erosion control	Erosion risk index	0–1	Decrease of erosion risk by vegetation in areas with a high erosion risk. To calculate the SES erosion protection, the erosion risk index was multiplied with data from the erosion map (decrease of erosion risk by vegetation, using indices	(Schulp et al., 2012)

			ranging from 0 to 1)	
	Soil retention	ton ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	Based on RUSLE ¹ , compares modelled soil erosion with and without the presence of vegetation. The difference between both outcomes, is referred to as soil retention	(Maes et al., 2012; Rendon et al., 2022)
Greenhouse gas and climate including carbon sequestration	Climate regulation by capturing CO ₂ by vegetation	%	Percentage of the annual country total CO ₂ emission that is captured by the ecosystem.	(Schulp et al., 2012)
	PESS ³	%	Indicator denotes the ratio of PESS to NPP _{pot} ⁴	(Mayer et al., 2021)
Primary/biomass production	Energy output from agricultural biomass	MJ ha ⁻¹	Energy content of agricultural production	(Mouchet et al., 2017)
Hydrological control	Soil infiltration capacity	mm	Calculated as the capacity of soil ecosystem to retain and process pollutants and excess of nutrients	(Maes et al., 2011)
	Water retention Index	(0-1) dimensionless	Takes into account the role of the water-holding capacity of the soil, and the relative capacity of both the soil and the	(Hölting et al., 2019)

			bedrock to allow percolation of water.
Habitat for biodiversity	Earthworm community metrics microbial, biomass, bacterial biomass, and bacterial diversity	(high, medium, low) dimensionless	Data for soil biological (earthworms and bacteria) and chemical (pH, soil organic matter, and nutrient content) attributes were used in the soil biodiversity model.
			(Rutgers et al., 2019)

RUSLE¹: Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation

PTRDB²: Pedo-Transfer Rules Database

PESS³: Primary and secondary biomass

NPPpot⁴ : Net primary production potential

Soil degradation due to erosion was mapped with indicators used for the spatial representation of degradation processes such as gully erosion, soil loss by water and wind and erodible fraction. Gully erosion indicator is composed by point data of gully erosion channels recorded during the in-field observations of LUCAS visual assessment inventory (Borrelli et al., 2022). In addition, soil loss by water was estimated with two approaches: first using RUSLE model, and second quantifying the potential of soil sediment transport at EU scale by the WaTEM/SEDEM model, considering the onsite soil loss and off-site effects of sediment transfer through the landscape (Borrelli et al., 2018). An integrated approach to map indicators for water and wind erosion, used the PESERA model which is a process-based model to quantify soil erosion by water, and RUSLE model (Gardi et al., 2013). The erodible fraction indicator was estimated based on a multiple regression equation for computing the erodible fraction of soils based on the soil texture and chemical properties (Borrelli et al., 2014).

Loss of diversity was mapped with indicators calculated on the basis of potential risk to soil microorganism, soil fauna and soil functions provided by soil organisms (Orgiazzi et al., 2016). Soil contamination was spatially represented using as indicators the concentration of trace elements in the topsoil (EU 28-member states) and soil contamination scores. In the first approach, the indicator was used to delineate the areas which are threatened by ten high trace elements concentrations and to establish the respective thresholds (Tóth et al., 2016). In the second approach, the indicator was represented by a map of contamination derived from Corine Land Cover 2000 map (Gardi et al., 2013). In addition, a third approach mapped the amount of microplastics per year contained in the sewage sludge applied to European agricultural lands (Lofty et al., 2022).

Soil organic carbon loss was mapped using soil organic carbon decrease. CENTURY process-based model was used to simulate carbon and nitrogen dynamics in natural or cultivated systems.

Consecutively, soil organic carbon loss was estimated combining a high-resolution erosion spatial layer based on RUSLE equation (Lugato et al., 2016). The indicator was based on the balance of the sediment transport and carbon fluxes in the eroding and depositional areas. Soil compaction was mapped using as indicator the map of natural susceptibility of soil to compaction compiled by JRC. The scores were attributed on the basis of the proposed classification of susceptibility to soil compaction (Classes 0–4) (Gardi et al., 2013). The ST salinization was spatially represented by saline and sodic class indicator, and the map of salt-affected soils in Europe. In this regard, salt affected soils of Europe are classified as saline and sodic soils. Saline soils are characterized by high salt content and sodic soils contain high proportion of exchangeable sodium. Both classes are important because they may limit agricultural potential (Ivits et al., 2013). The soil sealing indicator was computed as a high-resolution land monitoring layer of the EEA with European coverage. The multi-sensor and bi-temporal, orthorectified satellite imagery (IMAGE2006) was used to derive soil sealing data covering 38 countries of Europe (Maucha et al., 2010).

The soil drought was mapped using a combined drought indicator derived by combining the standardized precipitation index (SPI), the soil moisture index anomaly (SMA), and the fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation (FAPAR) anomaly. This indicator was used to identify areas susceptible to soil drought (Toreti et al., 2022). On the other hand, nutrient imbalance, soil acidification and waterlogging were mapped by Bridges and Oldeman, (1999) in the global assessment of human-induced soil degradation (GLASOD), nevertheless the authors do not provide information about the indicators used.

Table 3. Indicators used to map STs at European scale

Soil threat	Indicator	Unit	Description	Reference
Soil erosion	Gully erosion	(Points observations) dimensionless	This indicator represents the gully erosion channels recorded by the Gully erosion LUCAS visual assessment inventory.	(Borrelli et al., 2022)
	Erodible fraction (EF)	%	Indicator based on soil texture and chemical properties, calculated using multiple regression equation.	(Borrelli et al., 2014)
	Soil loss (water)	t km ⁻² yr ⁻¹	Represent mean annual soil loss rates by sheet and rill erosion.	(Panagos et al., 2020)
		Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	Represent annual rates of soil loss, sediment transfer and deposition.	(Borrelli et al., 2018)

	Soil loss (wind)	t ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	Represent the amount of soil eroded and transported by wind for a specified time period.	(Borrelli et al., 2018)
	Soil erosion (water and wind)	t ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹	Indicator derived from PESERA ¹ and the RUSLE ² models.	(Gardi et al., 2013)
Soil contamination	Concentration of trace element in topsoil	mg/kg	Represent the topsoil (0-30 cm) concentration of the following trace elements: As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Sb and Zn.	(Bridges & Oldeman, 1999; Tóth et al., 2016)
	Soil contamination scores	(44 classes) Dimensionless	Indicator derived from Corine Land Cover 2000 map.	(Gardi et al., 2013)
	Mean microplastics concentration	MP _p /m ² /yr.	Total daily microplastic flux and the mean daily sewage sludge production were used to calculate the concentration of microplastics.	(Lofty et al., 2022)
Soil organic carbon loss	Soil organic carbon decrease	Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	Account for SOC balance associated with the sediment transport and carbon fluxes considering eroding and depositional areas.	(Lugato et al., 2016)
Soil compaction	Natural susceptibility of soil to compaction map	(Classes 0-4) Dimensionless	Soil compaction is defined as an increase in bulk density and a decrease in soil porosity.	(Gardi et al., 2013)
Salinization	Saline and sodic class	(Classes) Dimensionless	Indicator used to represent saline and sodic soils.	(Ivits et al., 2013)

Soil sealing	Soil sealing (raster)	0 - 100%	Indicator derived from multi-sensor and bi-temporal, orthorectified satellite imagery (IMAGE2006).	(Maucha et al. 2010)
Soil drought	Combined Drought Indicator (CDI)	Dimensionless	Indicator used to identify areas that may be affected by agricultural drought.	(Toreti et al., 2022)
Nutrient imbalance	Loss of nutrients and organic matter indicator	Not information about the units	Not information available about the indicator	(Bridges & Oldeman, 1999)
Soil acidification	Soil acidification indicator	Not information about the units	Not information available about the indicator	
Waterlogging	Waterlogging indicator	Not information about the units	Not information available about the indicator	
Loss of diversity	Index of potential risk to soil microorganisms (PRMIC)	Dimensionless	Indicator calculated using the following maps: potential cultivation of GMOs ³ , potential risk of fragmentation, spatial distribution of the terrestrial invasive species, soil compaction, soil sealing, soil erosion, soil salinization, land use change, soil pollution, organic matter decline, intensive human exploitation	(Orgiazzi et al., 2016)

Index of potential risk to soil fauna (PRFAU)	Dimensionless	Indicator calculated using the following maps: potential cultivation of GMOs, invasive species, nuclear pollution, climate change, land use change, organic matter decline, intensive human exploitation.
Index of potential risk to functions provided by soil organisms (PRFUN)	Dimensionless	Indicator calculated using the following maps: potential cultivation of GMOs, invasive species, habitat fragmentation, nuclear pollution, soil compaction, industrial soil pollution, soil sealing, soil salinization, land use change, organic matter decline, intensive human exploitation.

PESERA¹: Pan European Soil Erosion Risk Assessment

RUSLE²: Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation

GMO³: Genetically modified organism

Since there is no agreement in the literature on the SES and ST Indicators names and definitions, indicators in various documents had to be reclassified in the framework of the SESs and STs of interest for this project (Annex I). The definitions of the indicators show that more than a simple difference of name, what lies behind is a difference of process measured (i.e., soil erosion by wind, water or tillage).

The WP2 (T2.3) is currently performing the selection and ranking of indicators of SESs and STs. We provided the list of SESs and STs identified at European scale, consequently they selected the most important indicators for SERENA project (Table 4).

Table 4. Indicators of major relevance selected by WP2 T2.3 of SERENA

SES/ST		Indicator	Unit
SES	Erosion control	Soil retention	ton ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹ of soil not eroded
		Soil loss by water erosion	Mg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
ST	Soil erosion	Soil loss by wind erosion	t ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹
		Soil organic carbon loss	Soil organic carbon decrease Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹

5.2 Methods used to map the soil ecosystem services and soil threats at the European scale

5.2.1 Soil ecosystem service assessment

We identified five approaches to model SESs (Annex IV). The first approach employed Bayesian networks. It is a graphical probabilistic model which connects explaining variables to soil function indicators through probability tables (Vrebos et al., 2018). The second approach used the IMAGE conceptual model for assessment of the relationship between ecosystem properties and the ecosystem service functions (ESF) (Schulp et al., 2012). The third article applied MESALES rule-based model to develop an indicator which represents the capacity of ecosystems to provide erosion control services (Maes et al., 2011). One article used the MIAMI deterministic model of climate net primary production of biomass (Neumann & Smith, 2018). Three studies applied a statistical model: the first identified synergies and tradeoffs (multinomial logistic regression) between ecosystem services (Maes et al., 2012), the second used multiple linear regression to assess SOC stock under future climate and land cover changes (Yigini & Panagos, 2016) and the third article used regression analysis in soil biodiversity prediction (Rutgers et al., 2019)(Figure 6).

Figure 6. SES assessment and modelling approaches

5.2.2 Soil ecosystem service mapping approaches

The ecosystem service mapping approaches are classified into six categories (Burkhard & Maes, 2017) (Annex V). In this literature review the selected documents based their mapping approaches in five out of the six categories. The C1 category groups articles in which mapping was performed using spatialized indicators (Mayer et al., 2021). Such indicators may be exhaustively spatialized (choropleth maps) or aggregated on land cover (e.g., CORINE land cover) or administrative areas (Rendon et al., 2022), nomenclature of territorial units for statistics (NUTS) regions (Jopke et al., 2015; Mouchet et al., 2017) and local administrative units (Hölting et al., 2019). Category C3 groups the studies in which spatially explicit indicators were extracted from the literature and used in the mapping attempt (Maes et al., 2012). Category C4 comprises articles that applied extrapolation methods from point observations (e.g., geostatistics) to estimate and map SESs (Maes et al., 2011).

Category C5 refer to models that combine field data (e.g., point-based measurements) and information from literature and expert knowledge linked to spatial data. Values are estimated using e.g., quantitative regression. Rutgers et al. (2019) was classified in the C5 category due to that the authors pointed out the limitation of the data availability of soil biodiversity to reproduce a map at European scale. In addition, the authors used point observations to predict (regression analysis) and map the soil biodiversity using digital soil mapping (DSM). Category C6 group studies that simulated or modeled ecosystem processes to identify changes in SESs. C6 category group four articles as follows: the first article performed a simulation and mapped the SES under environmental consequences of human activities (Schulp et al., 2012), the second and third articles focused on the simulation of SOC stock under future climate (Lugato et al., 2014) and land cover changes (Yigini & Panagos, 2016). The fourth article simulated carbon uptake (Neumann & Smith, 2018) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. SES mapping approaches identified in the gathered documents

5.2.3 Soil threat assessment and mapping approaches

Deterministic model, expert knowledge and statistical model were the most frequently used to assess STs (Annex V) (Figure 8). Deterministic model assume links between cause and effect. The Revised

Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) is a common example developed to better understand the factors driving soil loss in agriculture land (Burkhard & Maes, 2017). Deterministic models were used for the quantification and assessment of soil erosion. Models such as RUSLE (e.g., e-RUSLE, RUSLE2015) (Bosco et al., 2015; Lugato et al., 2016; Panagos et al., 2015, 2020; Právělie et al., 2017) PESERA (Panagos et al., 2014; Vanmaercke et al., 2012) and WaTEM/SEDEM (Borrelli et al., 2014) were used to estimate the ST and consequently the spatial representation was mapped with DSM. Statistical models are used when there is no known quantified relationship between components of the conceptual model. In this sense, statistical models can help to identify the relationships by drawing on collected data (Dunford et al., 2017). Statistical models were applied in the assessment and mapping of estimated soil erosion rates (Borrelli et al., 2017; Cerdan et al., 2010), concentration of soil pollution (trace elements) in topsoil (Tóth et al., 2016b), and soil sealing (Maucha et al., 2010).

The expert knowledge approach is used when the expert involvement provides valuable information in cases where other sources fail, producing results and validating maps (Jacobs and Burkhard, 2017). The expert knowledge approach was used in five documents to assess and map potential gully erosion (Borrelli et al., 2022), water erosion (Kay et al., 2019) soil loss by crop harvesting at NUTS2 level (Panagos et al., 2019), the status of soil degradation (soil erosion, chemical and physical degradation (Bridges & Oldeman, 1999) and in the estimation of the magnitude and spatial patterns of potential threats to soil biodiversity (Orgiazzi et al., 2016).

The direct approach is used when field experiments allow the direct measurement of the service (i.e., carbon stock) (Burkhard & Maes, 2017). The direct approach was used to assess and map ST in two articles. In the first article, the direct measurement of field observation (e.g., precipitation, soil moisture and FAPAR anomaly) were combined in a single indicator used to map soil drought (Toreti et al., 2022). In the second article, the direct measurement of the microplastic concentration in sludge used as soil amendment in agriculture land, was estimated and used to map soil pollution (Lofty et al., 2022). The proxy-based assessment and mapping is often based on digital raster land cover maps, and are subject to the availability of spatial data. This approach was identified in two documents where the spatial distribution of saline areas was mapped and assessed (Ivits et al., 2013; Tóth et al., 2016b). The spatial multicriteria evaluation combines and transforms spatial data (input) into a resultant decision. As a result, an aggregation of multidimensional information is obtained into a single parameter output map which represents the decision (Burkhard & Maes, 2017). The spatial multicriteria evaluation was used to assess and map landslide susceptibility (Günther et al., 2014; Wilde et al., 2018).

Rule-based modelling is often represented as nested decision trees. Additionally, rule-based models can be applied using Boolean decision (Burkhard & Maes, 2017). A rule-based modelling (cubist model) was applied to assess susceptibility to wind erosion, estimating the wind-erodible fraction of soil (EF) and mapping the interpolation of the EF values (Borrelli et al., 2014). The conceptual model is defined as the first phase of any computer modelling process. This model is used to understand linkages between different components of the system being studied (Burkhard & Maes, 2017). A conceptual model was used to estimate potential threats levels to soil biodiversity, mapping the composite indicator of pressure on soil biodiversity (Gardi et al., 2013). Metamodel is a model based on the collection of a set of models. A metamodel approach was used to estimate and map sediment fluxes by tillage erosion at 1km resolution (Van Oost et al., 2009).

Figure 8. ST assessment and modelling approaches

6 Soil ecosystem service and soil threat interactions (bundles, synergies and tradeoffs): how are they considered in mapping?

More than one SES or ST was often mapped in each publication. A co-occurrence network of SES and ST terms was performed using 12 SES and 29 ST documents. The co-occurrence network was used to produce a graphical representation of the collective interconnection of terms (e.g., SESs and STs) based on their paired presence within each document. Networks are generated by connecting pairs of terms using a set of criteria defining the co-occurrence. As a result, we obtained the graphical representation of the simultaneous occurrence of several SESs and STs reported in each mapping attempt, rather than the relationship between SESs and STs (e.g., bundles) (Figure 9). In this regard, the term nutrient decline (nutrient imbalance in SERENA SES priority list) only co-occurs with waterlogging which at the same time co-occurs with soil acidification, salinization, biomass production, and soil drought. In addition, a cluster of links between STs and SESs can be noted where SESs and STs show co-occurrence between them and always more than two co-occurrences. In particular soil erosion had strong link with erosion control and carbon sequestration. However, all of them have a co-occurrence with soil erosion. For instance, in SES assessment, soil erosion is mainly addressed by erosion control which describes the reduction of soil loss by vegetation cover (Potschin-Young et al., 2018). Soil erosion was mapped in 20 documents along with other STs, and is playing a central role linking different STs and SES (Figure 9). The capacity of agricultural ecosystems to provide SESs is related to the condition of the soil and their properties and functions. In this sense, the Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection of the European Commission, identifies soil erosion as the most important soil degradation process in EU member states, highlighting the importance of soil conservation (European Union, 2006). Soil erosion leads to soil degradation, in this sense, soil material, organic carbon and nutrients get lost resulting in reduced soil natural capital and decrease of SESs (Steinhoff-Knopp et al., 2021).

Figure 9. Co-occurrence network analysis of SES (n=13) and STs (n=29)

However, in most cases, despite co-occurrence of several SESs/STs, they were mapped individually without considering their interactions. Indeed, only three articles were identified as having assessed interactions among multiple SESs along with no soil-based ESs (SES+ES): two identifying synergies, trade-offs and one focused on bundles.

The first approach (Maes et al., 2012), aimed to report on a spatial assessment of the relationships between biodiversity and ESs including SESs (i.e., water infiltration capacity of soils and soil organic matter content). The authors standardized the different ecosystem service maps between 0 and 1 based on minimum and maximum values. Then the spatial synergies and trade-offs between multiple SESs+ESs and biodiversity were detected using a correlation biplot based on principal component analysis (PCA). The maps were summed to create maps of multiple ecosystem services depending on the correlation structure that was revealed by the PCA. Finally, using multinomial logistic regression model (MLRM), the relationship between habitat conservation status, SESs +ESs, and biodiversity was analyzed. A Monte Carlo analysis was used to test the uncertainty of the regression coefficients obtained from the MLRM. Based on this uncertainty analysis, the authors reported positive relationships observed between total ecosystem service supply and favorable habitat conservation status reflected a meaningful statistical pattern present in the data.

The second approach (Jopke et al., 2015) aimed to improve the previous approach assessing the interactions among different services beyond simple linear correlations as follows. First, the data used in the former articles (Maes et al., 2012; Maes et al., 2011) was used to evaluate the interaction

between ESs including SESs (i.e., erosion control, carbon storage). Second, a statistical analysis was performed to complement the former study's parametric statistics approach, by using bagplots (e.g., bivariate boxplots) to identify relations among pairs of SESs+ESs. Third, the cumulative correlation coefficient R was used as an index to rank SESs+ESs according to their potential synergies and trade-offs with all other services in the correlation matrix. Fourth, the SESs+ESs interactions were mapped on the level of NUTS regions. The drivers were implicit, with an unspecified threshold with absence of uncertainty estimation and validation.

The third approach (Mouchet et al., 2017) aimed to assess the spatial patterns of ES associations (bundles) in forests and agricultural lands. One SES (carbon sequestration) along with ten ESs (not soil based) and one disservice were quantified. Bundles were mapped at the extent of twenty-seven Member States of the European Union (EU27) on a 1 km² grid. The self-organizing map method was used to cluster locations according to their similarity using "kohonen" R package. In addition, the self-organizing map algorithm was set up to build two to twenty clusters and then the "silhouette width index" was used to define the optimal number of clusters. Consecutively, the multifunctionality of European regions was evaluated and mapped, as the ability of NUTS2 administrative levels to provide more than one bundle (clusters). The potential drivers (i.e., land cover, topography and climate factors) within each cluster were selected. Then, the co-variation of SES+ES indicators within each self-organizing map cluster was analyzed using a Redundancy Analysis (RDA). RDA is an appropriate method to regress several explanatory variables or drivers (i.e., agricultural land use intensity, degree of soil sealing) against multiple response variables (i.e., the eleven SESs+ESs indicators). The RDA combined with a stepwise procedure was used to select the cluster with the combination of variables (e.g., land cover, topography and climate factors) with the highest R^2 and p-value. Isolating variables (e.g., land cover, topography and climate factors) significantly affects the co-variation of multiple ESs. With this, the authors were able to isolate variables significantly affecting the co-variation of multiple SES+ES.

7 Model validation approaches

Models represent an essential tool used in the assessment of SESs and STs. Models quantify the SES/ST and allow spatial representation through maps. In this sense, model validation is a crucial practice due that is important to test the model validity against the known data (Dunford et al., 2017). Model validation is used to address model uncertainty. Nevertheless, to validate a model, it is mandatory to know what the true values should have been. This is difficult to achieve for some ES (e.g., cultural ES), particularly those that base their assessment in expert opinion (Dunford et al., 2017). Regarding SES, in this literature review, one document out of thirteen performed model validation. Yigini & Panagos (2016) randomly split the primary dataset into two parts: the calibration dataset (90%) to be used for model porpoises and the validation dataset (10%) used to compare and validate the output. On the other hand, validation was most common for STs assessment. Five documents out of 29 performed model validation (Figure 10).

Figure 10. SES and ST model validation

The validation approaches used for STs assessment and mapping are based on techniques such data splitting (e.g., cross-validation), and expert knowledge (Table 5). In the data splitting and cross-validation, the dataset is divided into a calibration (training) sample and a validation (test) sample. However, cross-validation produces much more stable results because it uses all data for validation and should be preferred over data-splitting (Brus et al., 2011). The expert knowledge or the qualitative validation is done when there is no possibility to apply metrics to evaluate the model performance.

Table 5. Validation approaches used in ST modelling

Model validation	Description	ST	SES
Data splitting	Samples from one (or several merged) samplings are split between a calibration and a validation dataset.	Tóth et al., 2016; Wilde et al., 2018	Yigini & Panagos (2016)
Cross-validation	Samples are split between a calibration and a validation dataset, and this is repeated until all samples have been in the validation set once.	Borrelli et al., 2014; Borrelli et al., 2017	-----
Qualitative validation (expert knowledge)	Expert knowledge is used to validate the model output	Borrelli et al., 2022	-----

8 Mapping soil ecosystem services and threats under different scenarios

Three articles mapping SESs or STs under different scenarios at the European scale were found. They mapped SOC stock, soil losses, decreasing and increasing SOC content in soil (Panagos et al., 2021; Podmanicky et al., 2011; Yigini & Panagos, 2016) (Table 5).

Lugato et al. (2014) aimed to create a baseline of SOC in EU agricultural soils with the main management practices (irrigation, mineral and organic fertilization, tillage, etc.) and to provide a powerful dynamic tool to orient future European policies for C sequestration. To this end, they established a comprehensive application of the pan-European model, using the agroecosystems SOC model CENTURY. They predicted the SOC stock in European scale for croplands under different climate change scenarios between 2010 and 2100, using the models and dataset from WorldClim.

Yigini & Panagos (2016) aimed at mapping the SOC stock at EU scale, under different scenarios, considering land cover and climate change using four representative concentration pathways (RCPs), projecting for the year 2050. They elaborated a digital soil mapping approach to map SOC stock at EU scale. SOC content from the LUCAS soil database was used as input, and covariates such as climate data available from the WorldClim Data Portal, which has climate projections every 20 years until 2100. They also used the land cover change to map the SOC stock, with the outputs of the “Land Allocation Module” of the LUMP platform. These data were utilized as input data to the interpolation modeling with regression kriging. First, they estimated the SOC stock for the baseline year of 2016, then utilized the fitted model to project the SOC stock to 2050 using the environmental variables as covariates. As a result of the model used, they considered an accuracy achieved as “relatively good”, with an R^2 of 0.4. Although the model fits the data to an acceptable level, the uncertainty is very high in northern Europe, especially northern UK, Ireland and Scandinavia. The dataset used (LUCAS) does not have samples above 1000 meters and the selection of soil sampling sites has an inherent bias towards agricultural land (predominantly under arable cultivation), which for the SERENA project would not be a problem, because we aim at this type of land use.

Table 6. Stocktaking of SESs and STs mapped in different scenarios in EU scale

Authors	SES or ST	Scenarios	Projection	Source of scenario models	Prediction models
(Yigini & Panagos, 2016)	SES: SOC stocks	Climate changes, atmospheric composition	2050	Climate: WorldClim (GCMs);	Multiple linear regression;
		and land use changes		Land use: LUMP, LUISA	Ordinary Kriging
(Lugato et al., 2014)	SES: SOC stocks	Climate change	2010 to 2100	WorldClim(GCMs)	CENTURY
(Panagos et al., 2021)	ST: Soil erosion by water	Future rainfall erosivity and	2050	Rainfall: WorldClim (GCMs);	RUSLE equation
		land use change		Land use: CAPRI and LANDUM	

(Podmanicky et al., 2011)	ST: Soil loss; SOC decrease	Land use change	2024	Land use: CLUE	RUSLE equation
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Regarding soil threats, Panagos et al. (2021), carried out the projection of soil losses from water erosion in Europe and UK with the impact of expected land use and climate change on future rates of soil erosion by water in 2050. They used different climate change scenarios, such as the RCP and erosivity of future rainfall from the WorldClim Data Portal, taking the year 2016 as a baseline, and estimating losses in the year 2050. They used three different RCPs (2.6, 4.5 and 8.5) as different climate scenarios and thus, using Gaussian Process Regression, estimated the R-factor of the RUSLE equation for the year 2050. Regarding future changes in land use, they used the projections provided by the Regional Impact Analysis of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAPRI) and the LANDUM model that had as output the C factor projections of the RUSLE model. Thus, using the RUSLE equation, they calculated the annual soil loss for the baseline and were also able to project for the year 2050.

Podmanicky et al. (2011) estimated soil loss, decrease and increase of SOC in soils at European scale, using the year 2000 as a baseline and projecting forecasts to 2024. They performed these estimates using land use change as different scenarios. The change in land use and land cover was predicted using the CLUE model - Conversion of Land Use and its Effects (<http://www.cluemodel.nl/>). CLUE is a dynamic, multi-scale land use and land cover change model developed at Wageningen University. To estimate the soil losses, they also used the RUSLE equation. For the land use change analysis, they only changed the C factor, since the other factors are less sensitive to land use changes. The change of SOC content (increasing or decreasing) was analyzed based on the land use and management changes, because different land use types are associated with characteristic SOC contents. The SOC content was calculated through the result of the CLUE model for each NUTS-X region.

The works found here mapped SESs and STs separately. No articles were found mapping bundles, trade-offs or synergy between SESs and STs on a European scale under different scenarios.

9 Final considerations

This report presents the state of art of the existing studies for agricultural soils on the mapping attempts of SESs and STs at the European scale individually or in interactions. Moreover, mapping attempts of the evolution of bundles of SESs and STs under different scenarios and management were considered.

Five SES out of seven of interest for SERENA project have already been mapped at European scale. On the other hand, the eleven STs of interest for SERENA project have already been mapped. The most frequently mapped SESs and STs were erosion control and soil erosion, respectively.

The SES publications are recent, whereas the ST publications have a relatively long history, beginning in 1999. The reduced number of publications on SESs (12) contrasted with the higher number of publications on STs (30). This indicates that mapping efforts at the continental scale have been focused on processes derived from STs, while less effort has been made on understanding the spatial SESs interactions and forecasting. Moreover, the total number of publications on mapping attempts of SESs and STs indicates that there is a need to conduct more research on SES, STs and bundles at EU scale in agricultural landscape.

One of the challenges faced in this literature review was the identification and selection of the SESs, STs and their respective indicators. In the literature, there is no agreement on the SES and ST definitions and indicators. In this way, the SESs and STs included in this report were selected based on the similarity of their definitions compared with the priority list and definitions provided by SERENA project.

In general, the assessment of SESs was based on conceptual models, deterministic and statistical model. Five SES mapping approaches were identified:

- 1- proxies of developed indicators and spatial data (i.e., CORINE land cover and NUTS);
- 2- spatially explicit indicators mapped from literature and statistics.
- 3- extrapolation methods to estimate and map SESs.
- 4- models that combine field data (e.g., point-based measurements) and information from literature and expert knowledge linked to spatial data.
- 5- approach based on simulation in which SES and climate and land cover changes are mapped.

Deterministic and statistical models along with expert knowledge were the most frequently used approaches to assess STs. Deterministic models were used for the quantification and assessment of soil erosion. Whereas, statistical models were applied in the assessment and mapping of estimated soil erosion rates, concentration of soil pollution (trace elements) in topsoil, and soil sealing. Expert knowledge was used to assess and map potential gully erosion, water erosion, and soil loss by crop harvesting.

Only three articles were identified as having assessed interactions among multiple SESs along with not soil-based ESs, including two identifying synergies, trade-offs, and one focused on bundles. The self-organizing map method or clustering approach is a suitable approach to be tested at European scale to identify SESs and STs bundles.

Four articles evaluating the evolution of SESs and STs under climate change and land use change scenarios were raised. This suggests that there is a need to cover this gap, being of paramount importance to monitor the evolution of SESs and STs and to identify methods for mitigating the reductions of SESs and the ST intensification. Furthermore, in the literature there is a gap of knowledge related with the forecasting of bundles of SES and ST in response to global change and land use change scenarios.

Model validation is an essential step in the assessment and mapping of SES and STs and is an important criterion for the reliability of the results. In this sense, the most reliable approach for SES was used by Yigini & Panagos (2016) (data splitting) in the assessment of soil organic carbon stocks under future climate and land cover changes. In addition, the most reliable approach for ST was developed by Borrelli et al. (2014, 2017) (cross-validation) to estimate wind erosion.

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Annex I

Soil-based ecosystem services and threats of interest selected by SERENA project

Table 1. Soil-based ecosystem services

Soil-based ecosystem services
Primary/biomass production
Habitat for biodiversity
Erosion control
Hydrological control
Environmental pollution control
Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration
Pest and disease control

Table 2. Soil threats

Soil threats
Soil erosion (water and wind, tillage)
Soil organic carbon loss
Nutrient imbalance
Soil acidification
Soil contamination
Soil compaction
Soil sealing
Salinization
Loss of diversity
Soil drought
Waterlogging

Annex II

Soil-based ecosystem services and threats definitions provided by SERENA, T2.2

PRIMARY/BIOMASS PRODUCTION

The capacity of soils to supply humans with food, feed, fiber, fuel, wood, pharmaceuticals and biochemical (based on definition given in LANDMARK).

HABITAT FOR BIODIVERSITY

An ecosystem able to sustain a community of living organisms which interact with one another, with plants, small animals and soil biota (micro, meso and macro-organisms) forming a biological network, controlling numerous soil functions and ecosystem services (based on definition given in MS selection sheet).

HYDROLOGICAL CONTROL

The capacity of a soil to receive, store and conduct water for subsequent use while minimizing the effects of prolonged droughts, flooding and erosion (Based on definition given in LANDMARK).

ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION CONTROL

The capacity of soil to sorb, reduce or eliminate the release and content of pollutants from the environment (MS selection sheet).

GREENHOUSE GAS and CLIMATE REGULATION / CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Greenhouse gas and climate regulation is defined as the capacity of a soil to reduce the amount of GHG emissions in the atmosphere (i.e., carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide). Carbon sequestration is the soil capability and integrated system of anthropogenic measures to increase soil C stock in individual horizon/whole soil profile (adapted from Vrebos et al., 2021).

PEST AND DISEASE CONTROL

Capacity of soil to prevent or control pests and diseases through soil biological activities and/or chemical/physical soil properties (based on several sources, MS selection sheet and e.g. <https://www.fao.org/ecosystem-services-biodiversity/background/regulating-services/en/>).

SOIL EROSION

Soil degradation process consisting of the detachment, disintegration and transport of soil particles by erosive agents, such as water (water erosion), wind (wind erosion), ploughing (erosion by tillage) or ice (glacial erosion). (Defined by Multilingual Dictionary of Soil Science of the Spanish Society of Soil Science. <https://cit.iec.cat/DMCSE/default.asp>).

SOIL ORGANIC CARBON LOSS

Decrease in soil organic carbon stocks or content of specific soil layers (from several SERENA-MS in the MS selection sheet).

NUTRIEN IMBALANCE

Nutrient imbalance is a deficiency or excess of one or more macro- or micronutrients at a given time (from several SERENA-MS in the MS selection sheet).

SOIL ACIDIFICATION

Soil acidification is an increase in soil acidity leading to unfavorable conditions for plant growth and microbe's activity. This involves a progressive loss of base cations from the soil exchange complex, which are replaced by aluminum ions and hydrogen ions with the consequent decrease in pH (based on definitions given in the MS selection sheet).

SOIL CONTAMINATION

Soil contamination is the occurrence of contaminants in soil above a certain level causing deterioration or loss of one or more soil functions, which can be in the form of point pollution and diffuse pollution. Soil pollutants can consist of various forms, such as organic and inorganic or particulate pollutants (taken from several SERENA-MS in the MS selection sheet).

WATERLOGGING

Temporary water inundation or undesired standing of water on soil surface due to both precipitation and groundwater emerging on the surface, that can limit oxygen access of the soil and create anaerobic conditions with the related negative consequences. Waterlogged soils can emit nitrous oxide (N₂O), as the most dangerous GHG and create anaerobic conditions in soil root zone (from several SERENA-MS in the MS selection sheet, in combination with definitions from LANDMARK % SOILCARE).

SOIL SEALING

Soil sealing can be defined as the permanent covering of soils by buildings, constructions and layers of completely or partly impermeable artificial material (asphalt, concrete, etc.). It is the most intense form of land take and is a hardly reversible process. Soil sealing is causing loss of essential soil ecosystem functions (Stolte et al. 2015).

SOIL COMPACTION

The densification and distortion of soil by which total and air-filled porosity are reduced, causing deterioration or loss of one or more soil functions.

SALINIZATION

Soil salinization is the process of accumulation of water-soluble salts within upper part of soil profile (particularly, A and B horizons) and when the accumulation is above a certain level adversely affects crop production, environmental health, and economic welfare (Tóth et al., 2008).

LOSS OF DIVERSITY

A reduction of forms of life living in soils (both in terms of quantity and variety) and of related functions (RECARE project).

Annex III

Source of the documents considered in the literature review

Fig 4. Source of the documents reporting mapping attempts of SESs (n=13) and STs (n=29) at the European scale in agricultural land

Annex IV

- Models represent an important tool used in the assessment of ESs. Models quantify the relationships that support ES supply, demand and flows, and the possibility to make spatial representation of such interactions through maps. The general types of methods and models used to assess SESs and STs at European scale are described below (Burkhard & Maes, 2017):
- Conceptual model: This kind of model is the first phase of any computer modelling process. They are used to understand linkages between different components of the system being studied.
- Deterministic models: Assume links between cause and effect. The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) is a common example developed to better understand the factors driving soil loss in agriculture land.
- Direct: this approach is used when field experiments allow the direct measurement of the service (i.e., carbon stock).
- Expert knowledge: approach in which the expert involvement provides valuable information in cases where other sources fail, producing results and validating maps (Jacobs and Burkhard, 2017).
- Proxy: proxy-based approaches on assessment and mapping are often based on digital raster land cover maps, and are subject to the availability of spatial data.
- Spatial multicriteria evaluation: process that combines and transforms spatial data (input) into a resultant decision. As a result, an aggregation of multidimensional information is obtained into a single parameter output map which represents the decision.
- Statistical model: where there is no known quantified relationship between components of the conceptual model, statistical models can help to identify the relationships by drawing on collected data.
- Rule-based modelling: this model is often represented as nested decision trees. Additionally, rule-based models can be applied using Boolean decision.
- Metamodel: Is a model that consists of statements about models. Metamodel is a model based on the collection of a set of models that are of interest in some specific topic.

Annex V

The ESs mapping approaches are classified into five categories as follows (Burkhard and Maes, 2017):

- Category 1 (C1): survey and census approaches provide spatial information which directly link ESs and STs to geographic information (e.g., land cover data). The land cover data is used as a proxy for different ESs.
- Category 2 (C2): Methods include expert estimates of ES values (e.g., lookup tables and delphi surveys).
- Category 3 (C3): mapping of ES based on indicators retrieved from literature or statistics (e.g., carbon sequestration can be estimated using statistics of carbon storage at different spatial scales).
- Category 4 (C4): extrapolation methods that estimate ESs (e.g., land cover classes) and STs from primary data
- Category 5 (C5): refer to models that combine field data (e.g., point-based measurements) and information from literature and expert knowledge linked to spatial data. Values are estimated using e.g., quantitative regression.
- Category 6 (C6): Andrew et al., (2015) recognizes an additional category of process models as simulation or modeling ecosystem processes to identify changes in ESs. Models required measurements for validation and calibration.

